

**INITIATIVES OF THE WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION AND THE
INTERNATIONAL OLYMPIC COMMITTEE FOR HEALTHY
LIFESTYLES ON INTERNATIONAL LEGAL ISSUES**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7416861>

Abstract: World Health Organization and International Olympic Committee initiatives to enhance international legal relations in sports are described in this article.

Keywords: International legal relations, sports legal relations, conventions, international treaties, international organizations

The World Health Organization (WHO) was established in 1948 to address international health problems. Among the statutory goals of the WHO is "the achievement of the highest possible level of health for all people" (art. 1) (1), including through physical culture and sports. As a result, certain aspects of international sports activities are regulated by WHO.

At its fifty-seventh session, WHO adopted the Global Strategy on Diet, Physical Activity, and Health. Paragraph 18 of the Global Strategy formulated its four main objectives: to reduce the two main risk factors for noncommunicable diseases - unhealthy diets and physical inactivity; expanding general awareness and understanding of the role of rational nutrition and physical activity as determinants of public health and the positive potential of preventive measures; encouraging the development, strengthening and implementation of global, regional, national and community policies and plans of action; collection of scientific data and monitoring of the main impacts on healthy nutrition and physical activity,

As stated in paragraph 23 of the Global Strategy, physical activity is a key determinant of energy expenditure that contributes to energy balance and weight maintenance. It not only reduces excess weight, but also improves many other conditions, including cardiovascular disease and diabetes. According to paragraph 24 of the Global Strategy, individuals should engage in an adequate amount of physical activity throughout their lives: "At least 30 minutes of moderate intensity physical activity on most days of the week reduces the risk of cardiovascular disease, diabetes, colon cancer, and breast cancer." In p. 25 of this document, in order to ensure successful prevention of chronic diseases, along with the above recommendations, the need for effective tobacco control is also indicated. P. 35-48 of the Global Strategy contain recommendations to states on

the development of national strategies in the area under consideration; paragraphs 49, 52-53, 56-57 list the main areas of interaction between WHO and other UN agencies and bodies; Paragraph 55 refers to the number of international partners with whom it is important to cooperate in achieving the set goals and objectives, not only UN agencies and other intergovernmental organizations, but also non-governmental organizations, professional associations, research institutes and the private sector. As stated in paragraph 60, civil society and non-governmental organizations have the following tasks to do: mobilize at the grassroots level and advocate for the inclusion of healthy diets and physical activity on the public agenda, provide information support for these initiatives, establish networks and action groups, organize campaigns and events, monitor performance (2). A concrete example of effective interaction between WHO and nongovernmental structures is the signing on July 21, 2010 of the Memorandum of Understanding between the World Health Organization and the International Olympic Committee in the field of promoting healthy lifestyles in Lausanne. Many non-communicable diseases, including 9 million people under 60, can be reduced through physical activity, according to the agreement. Inactivity is the fourth leading global risk factor, which results in 1.9 million deaths each year. Globally, this trend is becoming more and more evident. By 2015, 41.2 million people will die from non-communicable diseases. Together, WHO and IOC will promote a tobacco-free Olympics, physical activity for all, and action against childhood obesity. The Memorandum states that WHO and the IOC will work together at the international and national levels to reduce non-communicable diseases. According to WHO Director-General Margaret Chan, this agreement will expand our capabilities and scale up the fight against diseases that are the leading causes of death worldwide. It is essential to combat these diseases if we are to achieve sustainable development in the 21st century. In response, IOC President Jacques Rogge commented on the conclusion of the Memorandum of July 21, 2010, that both the IOC and WHO are committed to promoting a healthy lifestyle and ensuring the holding of sporting events at the grassroots level. This Memorandum is expected to contribute to the achievement of synergies in the declared areas. A working group has been established between the IOC and WHO that will meet annually to determine how to proceed.

References:

1. <http://apps.who.int/gb/bd/PDF/bd47/RU/constitutionru>
2. <http://www.who.int/dietphysicalactivity/strategy/eb11344/>

3. http://www.who.int/mediacentre/news/releases/2010/ioc_20100721/en/index